

Review

Rift Valley fever virus: A review of diagnosis and vaccination, and implications for emergence in Europe[☆]

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ABSTRACT

Rift Valley fever virus (RVFV) is a mosquito-borne virus, and is the causative agent of Rift Valley fever (RVF), a zoonotic disease characterised by an increased incidence of abortion or foetal malformation in ruminants. Infection in humans can also lead to clinical manifestations that in severe cases cause encephalitis or haemorrhagic fever. The virus is endemic throughout much of the African continent. However, the emergence of RVFV in the Middle East, northern Egypt and the Comoros Archipelago has highlighted that the geographical range of RVFV may be increasing, and has led to the concern that an incursion into Europe may occur. At present, there is a limited range of veterinary vaccines available for use in endemic areas, and there is no licensed human vaccine. In this review, the methods available for diagnosis of RVFV infection, the current status of vaccine development and possible implications for RVFV emergence in Europe, are discussed.

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1. Introduction

Rift Valley fever virus (RVFV) is a mosquito-borne virus of the genus *Phlebovirus*, family *Bunyaviridae* [1]. The RVFV genome is composed of three segments of single-stranded RNA, referred to as large (L), medium (M) and small (S) [2]. The bunyavirus ribonucleoproteins corresponding to each genomic segment appear circular when observed by electron microscopy [3], although a simplified schematic detailing the individual genome segments and gene order is shown in Fig. 1. The L segment encodes the viral RNA-dependent RNA polymerase (L protein) [4]. The S segment encodes the nucleoprotein (N) and the non-structural NSs protein, which is a major determinant of virulence [5,6]. The M segment encodes at least four proteins: the structural glycoproteins Gn and Gc, the non-structural protein Nsm, and a large 78-kDa glycoprotein (LGp) [7]. The structural glycoproteins mediate binding and entry via receptors on the target cell membrane. The function of

the 78-kDa glycoprotein is unclear, although it is thought to be incorporated into virions matured in mosquito cells, where it may facilitate transition between different host species, and function during replication in the mosquito host [8]. However, due to its ability to form a complex with the Gc glycoprotein [9], the 78-kDa glycoprotein may constitute a target for the immune system, and could potentially contribute to novel vaccine development. Additionally, the virus does not encode a matrix protein so the surface glycoproteins interact directly with the ribonucleoprotein [9].

RVFV is the causative agent of Rift Valley fever (RVF), a zoonotic disease affecting both ruminants and humans. In ruminants, RVF is characterised by neonatal mortality and an increased incidence of abortion or foetal malformation [2,10,11]. Sheep are the species of domestic animal most susceptible to RVFV infection, and new-born lambs in particular [10,11]. Mortality rate is significantly influenced by the age of the animal; newborn lambs are highly susceptible, with a mortality rate of greater than 90% in lambs less than a week old, associated with acute necrotic hepatitis [9,12,13]. However, the mortality rate in adult ruminants is generally lower, at 10–30% [14]. The abortion rate can range between 40 and 100% [13] (Fig. 2).

In comparison to the course of disease observed in animals, pregnant woman and neonatal infants are not preferentially affected [15]. Human infection with RVFV is generally asymptomatic, and the majority of those with clinical symptoms present

[☆] This review is dedicated to Professor Richard M. Elliott (1954–2015) for his friendship, support and outstanding contributions to virology, especially in the field of bunyavirus research.

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Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the segmented RNA genome of RVFV, detailing the small (S), medium (M) and large (L) segments in linear representation, adapted from [47]. The black shaded areas of this schematic diagram, denoted at the 3' and 5' end of each segment (not to scale), represent terminal sequences that are complementary to each other, forming panhandle structures that give rise to a circular appearance when observed using electron microscopy [15].

with a short febrile illness and no long term sequelae [16]. In some cases, fever recurs with headaches for up to 10 days followed by two weeks of weakness before recovery [17]. However, a small minority develop severe RVF disease, exhibiting early symptoms of acute hepatitis with associated jaundice, renal failure and haemorrhagic complications [18,19]. Haemorrhagic manifestations may include macular rash across the trunk of the body, ecchymosis on limbs and eyelids, bleeding from the gums and gastrointestinal

Fig. 2. Aborted sheep foetus. Picture courtesy of Professor Coetzer, University of Pretoria, South Africa, made available through the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) Corporate Document Repository (<http://www.fao.org/docrep/006/y4611e/y4611e05.htm>) [accessed on 12th June 2015].

mucosal membranes, low blood pressure, hematemesis, melaena and hepatosplenomegaly [20,21]. If the patient survives the hepatitis, neurological manifestations may include loss of vision and signs of encephalitis [16]. The risk of fatality increases for patients with jaundice, encephalitis or haemorrhagic disease, with a fatality rate of 1–3%, which can be as high as 50% in patients with haemorrhagic complications [16]. Long-term sequelae are observed in a small number of patients, where neurological disorders resulting from encephalitis may lead to blindness, hemiparesis, quadriplegia, incontinence, hallucinations, locked-in syndrome or coma [22–24].

Animals become infected through a bite from an infected mosquito, and there are a number of mosquito vectors that have been shown to be naturally infected with RVFV, predominantly of the *Culex* and *Aedes* genera (reviewed in [25]). The transmission cycles of RVFV are summarised in Fig. 3. In addition, there can also be animal-to-animal infection through direct contact with infected tissues or fluids [15], and animals may also become infected through the re-use of needles during vaccination; particularly in regions with limited resources [26]. There may also be the potential for lactating animals to infect their young via milk [27–29]. Human infection can also arise from a mosquito bite [30]. However, humans can become infected through exposure to infected animals or animal tissues, since infected animals, and sheep in particular, can display high titre viraemia [31]. Following infection with RVFV, both the innate and adaptive immune responses are important for virus clearance [14,32]. Along with an innate immune response, natural infection with RVFV in domestic ruminants leads to the development of a neutralising antibody response, elicited by the viral glycoproteins (Gn and Gc) and the nucleocapsid protein [33–35].

RVF disease was first reported in 1930, as a result of investigations into a high abortion rate amongst pregnant ewes accompanied by a high mortality rate of newborn lambs, on a farm in the Rift Valley region of Kenya, and the causative agent was identified as a virus [10]. Many of the people who had come into contact with infected animals and tissues developed illness characterized by fever, headaches and malaise; one individual developed a second fever accompanied by headaches, and retained defective vision for a number of weeks afterwards. Subsequently, periodic outbreaks occurred in Kenya and other east African countries including Tanzania and Zambia [36,37], until RVFV was identified in South Africa in 1951 [38]. The disease is now considered to be endemic in sub-Saharan African countries, with periodic major outbreaks occurring throughout much of the African continent, associated with episodes of heavy rainfall and flooding [39] (Fig. 4). Over the past forty years, RVFV has been detected in African countries outside its traditional enzootic region, including Egypt in 1977 [40], and west Africa, in Mauritania and Senegal in 1987 [41,42]. A further outbreak occurred in Mauritania in 2010 [43]. In 1990, an outbreak of RVF was confirmed outside of mainland Africa for the first time, on the Indian Ocean island of Madagascar [44]. In 2000, RVFV was also detected in Saudi Arabia and Yemen [14,45], and by 2007 its geographical range included the French island of Mayotte in the Comoros Archipelago [46]. Likely explanations for the detection of epizootics outside the usual RVFV enzootic regions are the commercial movement of infected animals and possibly windborne movement of infected mosquitoes [47]. The emergence of RVF in the Middle East and Mayotte has highlighted that RVFV may be increasing its geographical range, giving rise to the concern that it may potentially reach the Mediterranean basin and Europe. Outbreaks of RVFV cause a significant disease burden, with large numbers of livestock and humans affected. The outbreak in Saudi Arabia in 2000 resulted in the death of an estimated 40,000 animals from a range of species, with 8000–10,000 abortions in ruminants [48]. Therefore, an incursion of this zoonotic virus into Europe could potentially have a devastating impact on the livestock industry in

Fig. 3. Schematic detailing the transmission cycles of RVFV; vectorial transmission (solid green arrows), direct transmission (solid red arrow) and vertical transmission (dashed red arrows). Red asterixes indicate where vaccine intervention would be appropriate. Adapted from an image available at (<https://www.pasteur.fr/en/research/virology/units-groups/arboviruses-and-insect-vectors/research>) [accessed on 12th June 2015]. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

multiple countries, along with a significant impact on animal and human health. The current status of diagnosis and vaccine development for RVFV infection are reviewed, and the factors which may exacerbate the potential emergence of RVFV in Europe are assessed.

2. Diagnosis of Rift Valley fever in animals and humans

Early detection of suspected cases is pivotal to ensure timely control measures are implemented to reduce the disease

burden. The sudden onset of large numbers of abortions ('abortion storms') and mortalities among young animals in affected livestock, together with the appearance of the disease in humans, is considered characteristic of an RVF epidemic [49]. In humans, the clinical recognition of acute haemorrhagic fever cases generally triggers an outbreak investigation in endemic regions. However, clinical diagnosis alone cannot be considered reliable as some animals, for example camels, may have inapparent infections. Moreover, infection of susceptible, adult non-pregnant ruminants is often

Fig. 4. Map detailing the distribution of RVF—data as of 2014, adapted from a map courtesy of Centers for Disease Control [CDC], Atlanta, USA (<http://www.cdc.gov/vhf/rvf/distribution-map.html>) [accessed on 12th June 2015]. Countries with endemic RVF and significant outbreaks are shown in red, countries with periodic cases of RVF and/or serological evidence of infection are shown in yellow, and countries with no reported cases of RVF or evidence of infection are shown in green. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

subclinical and hence outbreaks outside of the lambing or calving seasons can be easily missed. The clinical signs of RVF in animals tend to be nonspecific and differential diagnoses includes brucellosis, Bluetongue, Wesselsbron disease, enterotoxemia, Bovine ephemeral fever, vibriosis, trichomonosis, Nairobi sheep disease, heartwater, ovine enzootic abortion, toxic plant ingestion, bacterial septicaemias, peste des petits ruminants, anthrax and Schmallenberg disease [50].

Reference laboratories are often responsible for the coordination of field sampling and testing but with heterogeneous laboratory coverage in some endemic regions, delays in diagnosing

the disease commonly occur. Laboratory diagnosis would ideally rely upon a combination of serological and molecular approaches. The usefulness of the chosen assay is dictated by the disease kinetics i.e. the window in which particular virological markers (e.g. virus, viral RNA, IgG, IgM, hepatic lesions) are likely to be detected. There is likely to be some variability in disease kinetics between humans and animal species due to variation in susceptibility between species, and even within species [2,51,52]. RVFV can be detected by classic virological methods which include virus isolation [53], histopathology [54], antigen detection [55,56], antibody detection [57–59] and nucleic acid based assays [60–62]. For

reporting RVFV in animals, the Office International des Epizooties (OIE); World Organisation for Animal Health, require laboratory confirmation by at least two positive results from a combination of different diagnostic approaches preferably for the same specimen i.e. either positive for virus/viral RNA and antibodies or positive for IgM and IgG with demonstration of rising titres between paired serum samples collected 2–4 weeks apart [50].

2.1. Histopathology

The collection of diagnostic tissues (e.g. liver) in formaldehyde in the field may be beneficial in remote areas where cold chains do not exist. The histopathological examination of the liver of affected animals (and humans) will reveal hepatic lesions characteristic of RVFV and immunostaining may allow the specific identification of RVF viral antigen in tissue [50,54].

2.2. Virus isolation

RVFV can be isolated from whole blood or serum collected during the acute (febrile) stage of the disease [53]. Post-mortem, the virus can also be isolated from the brain, liver, spleen and organs of the aborted foetus. *In vivo* isolation of RVFV can be performed in suckling mice; however, the OIE recommends that this approach should be avoided in favour of *in vitro* virus isolation, due to animal welfare and biosafety issues [50]. There are various cell cultures that can be successfully employed for *in vitro* isolation of RVFV including African green monkey kidney cells (Vero), baby hamster kidney (BHK) cells and AP61 mosquito cells. Mammalian cell lines are generally preferred for RVFV isolation due to the consistent cytopathic effect (rounding of the cells), with destruction of the cell monolayer within 12–24 h post infection. Immunostaining or reverse-transcription polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) can be used to confirm virus isolation.

2.3. Serology

Serological diagnosis, usually by virus neutralisation assay (VNA) or enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA), is commonly used to confirm RVFV infection in an affected individual (animal or human), during outbreak management and also to determine the prevalence of exposure to RVFV in a susceptible population (surveillance). Several assays are available for the detection of anti-RVFV antibodies in a variety of animal species. Both the VNA and ELISAs are highly specific, although there is the potential that they could be hindered by cross-reactivity between RVFV and other phleboviruses [15]. Alternative techniques such as the Indirect Immunofluorescence, agar gel immunodiffusion (AGID), radioimmunoassays and complement fixation are no longer used [50]. The haemagglutination inhibition assay (HIA), once widely applied for serological investigations of suspected animals, is now rarely used due to biosafety and logistical issues.

The Virus Neutralisation Assay is the gold standard serological assay, generally used for vaccine potency determination and is the OIE prescribed test for international trade [50]. The test is highly specific and, unlike some ELISA based assays, can be applied to serum from a wide range of host species. However, virus neutralisation assays can only be performed in appropriate biosecurity facilities as they involve the manipulation of live virus. Alternative RVFV neutralisation assays are being developed and validated, which eventually may lead to assays which do not involve the handling of highly virulent RVFV in containment [63].

ELISAs can be employed to confirm the presence of either specific IgM antibodies, which appear transiently from 4 days after infection or specific IgG antibodies, which appear from 8 days after infection and may persist for several years [64,65]. The

appearance of antibodies, usually following four to seven days of clinical symptoms/signs, generally coincides with the gradual disappearance of the virus in the blood. Hence, either serum or blood samples collected for serological analysis may contain live virus and must therefore be inactivated prior to testing outside of biocontainment. ELISAs are developed and widely applied by OIE Reference Laboratories [50,65], and several have been developed using either whole cell lysate derived from infected cells or purified nucleocapsid protein as antigen [65–69]. However, the commercially available ELISAs (IgG and IgM) are based upon recombinant RVFV nucleocapsid protein, despite the potential for high background issues with this antigen [70]. The detection of IgM would suggest a current or recent infection. However, IgG-based ELISAs cannot distinguish between past and current infection unless paired serum samples are analysed (acute and convalescent) and a four-fold increase in antibody titre observed.

An indirect ELISA based on the recombinant nucleocapsid protein of RVFV has been developed for the detection of specific antibodies in human and animal sera [67]. This dual target assay is designed to differentiate between infected and vaccinated animals (DIVA), an important factor when considering the financial burden of movement restrictions on suspect livestock and the regulatory requirements for vaccine licensing. In naturally occurring infections, an antibody response against both N and NSs would be expected whereas in individuals vaccinated with the attenuated vaccines (Δ NSs) only an antibody response to the N protein would be observed [67].

A selection of European laboratories recently participated in a ring trial, to directly compare their own ELISAs with those from other laboratories, along with a number of commercially available ELISAs [59]. It was concluded that, whilst further evaluations are warranted particularly for IgM ELISAs, their ring trial supports the use of commercially available ELISAs for both primary screening and serological diagnosis.

2.4. Molecular methods

A more economical and rapid alternative to virus isolation is the detection of viral RNA during the acute (febrile) phase of the disease, when high levels of viraemia occur in both humans and animals. After an initial incubation period of 2–6 days in humans, the febrile phase occurs, and typically lasts 3–4 days [2,71,72]. Thus, rapid responses are necessary to allow case confinement (to avoid nosocomial infections in humans) and provide appropriate management and control decisions. A range of highly sensitive nucleic acid based molecular tests have been developed for RVFV including nested RT-PCR methods [61], quantitative real-time PCR [60,73–78], multiplex PCR-based macroarray assay [79], RT Loop-mediated isothermal amplification (RT-LAMP) [62] and recombinase polymerase amplification (RPA) [80].

The RVF RT-LAMP amplifies specific nucleic acid sequences using a set of six primers by strand displacement activity of a DNA polymerase [62,81]. Amplification leads to the formation of a DNA precipitate which is detectable by the naked eye. There is no requirement for complex equipment and the assays can be cheaply and easily applied in field situations. The RVF RPA method [80], an alternative isothermal amplification method utilising three oligonucleotides and a specific fluorescent probe, has been shown to be as sensitive as LAMP and quantitative real time RT-PCR (qRT-PCR), but with the greater potential to be applied to a hand held battery operated device for point of care or field application.

The OIE recommends that viral RNA detection is undertaken using locally validated methods [50], such as conventional gel based RT-PCR or real-time RT-PCR. In a recent external quality assessment (EQA), thirty expert laboratories from 16 countries tested a blind panel of RVFV positive and negative samples using their local

molecular based RVFV test procedures. Twenty-eight of the thirty laboratories (93%) reported the use of a qRT-PCR for which consistently high sensitivity and specificity was observed between the laboratories, although less consistency was observed for the nested RT-PCR assays. Escadafal et al. [82] also highlighted the limitations of employing highly specific probe based or nested molecular assays, which may fail to detect the wide range of potentially circulating RVFV strains. The two more recently developed molecular assays (RT-LAMP and RPA) were also represented in the ring trial, albeit by single laboratories, and compared well to the qRT-PCR.

Whilst molecular techniques have proven useful during RVF outbreaks [49], the short duration of viraemia (3–4 days [2,71,72]), and the dependence on specialised equipment and skills, still pose challenges to their widespread applicability for monitoring the spread of the virus in the field. However, molecular approaches allow for the rapid identification of the genetic lineages and hence the source and pathogenicity of the viral strains involved in a RVF outbreak [83]. In addition, the RVF viral load is predictive of disease outcome, thus the use of quantitative real time assays may enable clinicians to target individuals with high viral loads (poor prognosis) for special intensive clinical management [84]. Sensitive and specific molecular assays may also be used for the early detection of RVFV RNA in mosquito pools thereby contributing to disease surveillance, vector species identification and disease control [45,77,85].

3. Vaccination and vaccine development

Vaccination to protect against RVFV remains problematic. Whilst there are no licensed vaccine preparations for use in humans, three licensed veterinary vaccines are being utilised to protect ruminant populations, which are summarised in Table 1. Despite the availability of the licensed live attenuated (Smithburn vaccine) and inactivated vaccine preparations, both have limitations to their use in endemic regions. Additionally, the live attenuated MP-12 vaccine has conditional licensure in the US, and the Clone-13 vaccine has also been licensed in South Africa and Zimbabwe [50]. However, the potential for co-infection and reassortment between vaccine and wildtype viruses, suggests that there is still an urgent requirement for a new generation of veterinary RVFV vaccines, and a safe and efficacious human vaccine. A successful vaccine would predominantly be applied throughout Africa, mainly in resource-limited settings, therefore a consideration of the cost to the farmer would be a particularly important part of the development process.

3.1. Inactivated vaccines

As for many viral pathogens, the development of vaccines for RVFV started with the use of inactivated material. The first reported preparation, the Entebbe vaccine, was based on a formalin inactivated mosquito derived virus that had undergone repeated passage in mice. The first inactivated vaccine was named NDBR103 and

represented the 184th passage of the Entebbe strain followed by amplification in African Green Monkey cells to produce a large stock from mouse sera [86]. This vaccine was utilised for vaccination of a group of 963 UN soldiers on a three-dose regime. Of those that received all three doses (administration of 1 ml subcutaneously on days 0, 7–10 and 28–30) the majority seroconverted with the highest antibody titres being reached six weeks post-vaccination [87]. A further development of this formalin-fixed vaccine was made with the production of TSI-GSD 200, a variation on the original preparation that was also trialled with the vaccination of service troops. Data from a 12-year trial supports the longevity of protective response for this latter preparation suggesting that TSI-GSD-200 provides long-term immunity in vaccinated humans following a primary inoculation and single boost schedule [88]. Whilst such inactivated preparations can elicit a neutralising response, the requirement for booster vaccinations makes utility within a predominantly resource-limited agricultural setting problematic [89]. As such, live attenuated vaccines were developed, for use in animals and humans.

3.2. Live attenuated vaccines

The Smithburn live attenuated RVFV vaccine was first developed in Uganda for use in animals in the 1950s following repeated passage of a mosquito-derived virus in mouse brain. The vaccine is significantly attenuated and has been used proactively in Kenya and South Africa. Despite the successes seen with the Smithburn vaccine, problems regarding residual pathogenicity have been reported, and furthermore the potential for teratogenic and abortifacient effects following administration have been observed. This was demonstrated by Botros et al. [90] who reported that administration of the vaccine to European breeds of cow ($n = 100$) led to abortion in 29% of pregnant animals. A group of twenty pregnant buffaloes were also vaccinated in this study with no abortions being reported. Sample size prevented statistical assessment of the study although molecular tests demonstrated that abortion was most likely caused by foetal infection following vertical transmission of vaccine virus [90]. Therefore, whilst this vaccine has found some utility in agricultural practices, the potential for reversion to virulence has meant that the vaccine is contraindicated in areas where RVFV has not been detected. Further studies are required to establish the determinants of virulence for this vaccine. Additionally, molecular analysis has suggested that reassortment among RVFV isolates may occur in nature, which has implications for vaccination with live attenuated vaccines during an outbreak [91]. The use of such vaccines during an outbreak may lead to the vaccination of a viraemic animal, providing an opportunity for reassortment between wild and vaccine viruses, which has the potential to increase the diversity of circulating RVFV strains [47]. Reassortants containing one attenuated and two virulent segments have been shown to be attenuated [92], therefore a reassortment event between a wild and vaccine strain could produce an attenuated virus which may protect against RVF,

Table 1
List of veterinary RVFV vaccines available [50,100]. *n/a* = not applicable.

	Smithburn live attenuated virus vaccine	Inactivated virus vaccines	Clone-13 live attenuated virus vaccine	MP-12 live attenuated virus vaccine
Virus origin	Mosquito, Uganda, 1948	Field strains (South Africa and Egypt)	Human, 1974	Human strain ZH548 (Egypt, 1977)
Attenuation	>200 passages in mouse brain	<i>n/a</i>	Natural deletion in NSs gene	Multiple mutations in S, M and L segments
Production medium	BHK cells	BHK cells	Vero cells	MRC-5 cells
Regimen	Single dose	Requires booster and annual revaccination.	Single dose	Single dose
Licensed	Yes	Yes	Yes—South Africa and Zimbabwe	Conditionally licensed in US

as long as attenuation markers were present in each segment of the live attenuated vaccine strain [91].

3.3. Alternative vaccines

Alongside the licensed vaccines a number of alternative vaccines have been developed that may, in the future, serve as appropriate preparations for effective vaccination. Such alternatives result from chemical treatment of existing preparations, further passage in a variety of species or development of recombinant vaccines using reverse genetics techniques.

3.3.1. Clone 13

The Clone 13 vaccine is based on a naturally attenuated strain, which contains a large deletion in the main virulence factor, the NSs gene [93]. Clone 13 is a plaque-derived clone of a Central African strain of RVFV isolated from a human, which was shown to be highly immunogenic, yet avirulent in mice and hamsters [93]. Experimental vaccine trials in mice and ruminants have suggested that this vaccine is safe, with no apparent side effects [5,94,95], and as such offers a further alternative to the Smithburn vaccine. However, intranasal inoculation with an NSs-deleted virus has been shown to cause severe neurological disease in mice [96], implying that NSs-deleted viruses may still retain some virulence.

3.3.2. MP-12

A live attenuated vaccine for both human and animal use was generated following passage of human strains in the presence of chemical mutagens [97]. The passage of isolates in the presence of 5-fluorouracil led to the establishment of a live attenuated virus that is temperature sensitive, and has been found to contain mutations in all three of its genome segments, a feature of importance when considering the potential for reversion to virulence. The resulting virus, termed MP-12, has been used to determine regions of the RVFV genome that are important for attenuation with the conclusion that mutations to the M and L segments primarily contribute to attenuation seen in a murine model [92,98,99], although mutations in the S segment also contribute to attenuation to a lesser extent [100]. The assessment of MP-12 in both animal and human vaccination trials have been encouraging with minimal teratogenic effects seen in ruminants [101,102] and suitable immunogenicity in non-human primates following a high dose intravenous or aerosol challenge [103] being reported. Interest in this preparation as a human vaccine is high and warrants further investigation.

3.3.3. Recombinant vaccines

Aside from the use of either killed vaccines or live attenuated vaccines, the use of viral products including antigen and heterologous vectors to express antigen has been assessed for RVFV. Standard viral vectors that have found utility in elimination of other viral diseases through expression of heterologous genes have been assessed. Historically, one of the most successful vectors for glycoprotein expression are poxviruses [104], and these viruses have been used as vectors for RVFV proteins previously [105,106]. Building on seminal studies, recombinant vaccinia viruses expressing Gn and Gc have been assessed in backbone strains of vaccinia that contain immunostimulatory genes cloned in place of vaccinia virulence genes. Preparations were shown to remain highly attenuated in both mice and non-human primates and were able to generate good neutralising antibody titres although further studies in ruminants are warranted [107]. Similarly, a replication-deficient chimpanzee adenovirus vector encoding RVFV envelope glycoproteins Gn and Gc induced a neutralising antibody and robust CD8+ T cell response in mice [108]. Related to this, a further study reported the use of another ruminant pathogen as a vehicle for RVFV glycoprotein expression to generate a bivalent DIVA vaccine for RVFV that had

the additional advantage of protecting animals against Lumpy Skin Disease virus (LSDV) [35,109]. This form of vaccine elicited protection against sheep pox and RVFV as well as neutralising antibodies to both LSDV, RVFV and the closely related capripox virus following vaccination. No adverse effects were seen following vaccination and as such this formulation represents a promising bivalent DIVA vaccine for LSDV and RVFV [35,110,111]. Other preparations involving modified vaccinia virus Ankara (MVA) expression of GnGc have also been assessed in murine models and may also represent future alternatives for vaccine development [111]. Importantly, recombinant pox virus based vaccine preparations offer DIVA potential that is not seen with other vaccines, with the exception of Clone 13, which also offers the potential for DIVA albeit through the absence of the NSs gene [15,112]. Other preparations including subunit vaccines [33,113,114] and DNA vaccines [115–117] have all been developed but are often poorly immunogenic and require several inoculations to elicit high titre neutralising antibodies (reviewed in [118]).

Reverse genetics-based vaccines have been developed for RVFV, and the ability to make cDNA copies of each segment of the RVFV genome and rescue live virus *in vitro* has had significant implications for the generation of novel vaccines across many virus families [119–123]. Avirulent recombinant RVFVs have been developed and tested in both rodents [112] and ruminants [124–126], and an MP-12 vaccine with an NSm deletion has been shown to be immunogenic in calves [125]. This approach also has the benefit of potentially complying with DIVA, although there is currently no data on NSm antibody prevalence in RVFV-positive sera to confirm the NSm as an effective antibody absence DIVA marker. As an additional alternative to the existing preparation, the MP-12 strain has been generated from clones, and a recombinant virus produced, where the genetic makeup has been altered from tri-segmented to bi-segmented [127]. The advantage of this recombinant is the removal of the potential for segment reassortment following co-infection with wild-type virus that could have implications for biosafety. A further adaptation to the MP-12 strain has been made through the deletion of the NSs gene, thus combining the advantages of the original MP-12 strain with elements of the Clone 13 vaccine that enable DIVA [128]. However, the NSs protein is known to elicit a variable antibody response in naturally-infected ruminants, which questions the application of NSs-specific antibodies as criteria to differentiate natural infection from vaccination [129]. MP-12 has also been genetically-modified to encode a mutant envelope protein, which created a mutant single-cycle replicable vaccine which did not cause any clinical disease in mice [130]. A critical development using a thorough understanding of RVFV molecular biology has been the ability to rescue recombinant virus-like particles (VLPs) and intact viruses. VLPs generated from the nucleoprotein [131] and glycoproteins [132] have been developed as potential vaccines against RVF. A number of groups have successfully recovered virulent and avirulent strains of the virus and utilised this technology to investigate the function of RVFV proteins [133–135]. This achievement has opened the way for defining the mechanisms of avirulence and for intelligent design of a vaccine against RVF. However, the main disadvantages for this approach are based upon resistance to the use of genetically recombinant products, particularly in humans, and animals entering the food-chain. Further studies with such recombinant vaccines are certainly warranted to assess applicability in the field.

4. RVFV emergence implications for the lack of available vaccine

Predicting the emergence and spread of RVFV has been the subject of considerable research in recent years. One area of

particular development has been the application of spatial modelling using environmental parameters to predict RVF outbreaks. Satellite images of sea surface temperatures, rainfall anomalies, and vegetation have been incorporated into models and have successfully predicted RVF outbreaks in sub-Saharan Africa [136,137]. This multi-disciplinary predictive surveillance for RVF has also been extended to aid in preparedness for a range of vector- and water-borne diseases (including leishmaniasis, malaria, dengue fever, Japanese encephalitis, chikungunya fever, tick-borne infections, Ebola virus disease and other haemorrhagic fevers, hantavirus disease) throughout regions of the Americas, Africa and Asia [138]. Under a multidisciplinary programme, initiated by the US Global Emerging Infections Surveillance and Response System (DoD-GEIS), data sets and information derived from eco-climatic remote sensing activities, ecologic niche modelling, arthropod vector, animal disease host and human disease surveillance for febrile illnesses, are collated into a predictive surveillance model. The model generates advice and alerts on emerging infectious disease outbreaks (early warning system). In combination with improving rapid field based diagnostics and sero-surveillance programmes, such model based approaches will support the early detection of emerging disease outbreaks and contribute to timely public health responses [139]. More recently, methods to link mathematical models for RVFV with broad-scale spatiotemporal data for realistic landscapes have been developed to assess receptivity for RVF [140]. This data-driven model was applied to the Central Valley of California to assess the threat RVFV poses to North America, and has the potential to assist in the prioritisation of when and where to focus control strategies, including animal vaccination, during an epidemic.

The expansion of RVF to the Middle East, in association with a changing climate and an increase in livestock trade has highlighted RVFV as a threat to Europe. The importation of millions of sheep and goats from RVFV-endemic regions of Africa to the Middle East for ritual slaughter during festival periods is one potential route for the introduction of RVFV to Middle Eastern countries and potentially the Mediterranean basin [141,142]. It should be noted however, that at present Egypt protects livestock from RVF by vaccination, although there are some import cases along the Sudan border. Saudi Arabia and Yemen only appear to have activity in a shared epidemic zone along the west coast. However, the proximity of Mediterranean countries to areas with endemic RVF, periodic cases or serological evidence of RVF is highlighted in Fig. 4. This is a concern which cannot be ignored, since high numbers of RVFV-competent mosquito vector species are present in Europe [143], and modelling studies have suggested that climate change has the potential to increase the risk of incursion of other competent mosquito species for RVFV into Europe [144]. However, a possible reason why RVFV has not yet spread into Europe may be the seasonality of temperatures and vector populations, which leads to conditions which are perpetually changing [140]. This may limit the opportunity for RVFV to become established in European mosquito populations, since variation in climate, vector and host density would influence vector competence, vectoral capacity and vector lifespan, in comparison to the more stable temperatures observed in Africa [25]. This also implies that an incursion may not progress to a large scale outbreak in Europe, although there remains an increased risk of RVFV entering Europe via the Mediterranean basin, through uncontrolled livestock movement associated with growing human populations and the increased demand for meat [25].

There are therefore a number of considerations which should act as drivers to progress vaccine development, including the presence of competent mosquito vectors in Europe. More than 65 mosquito species are described as potential vectors of RVFV worldwide, with species in the genera *Aedimorphus* (*Aedes*), *Culex*, *Anopheles*,

Neomelaniconion and *Ochlerotatus* considered natural hosts and primary vectors [25,145–148]. Of the vectors identified as competent for RVFV, a number are present in Europe, including *Culex pipiens s.l.* Therefore, the emergence of the virus in Europe may have the potential to spread rapidly throughout resident mosquito populations, and lead to an epidemic. Furthermore, climate change may lead to an increase in the already high numbers of RVFV-competent mosquito vector species in Europe, and an increase in risk of incursion of RVFV into Europe [25,143,144]. This has been investigated through modelling studies in the Netherlands, which identified some regions with a high transmission potential for RVFV, along with a risk of persistence of infection [149]. This study showed that the areas most at risk in the Netherlands had a low density of livestock, and therefore a high vector–host relationship, and that the risk of persistence is due to the presence of *Culex pipiens s.l.* rather than the less abundant *Aedes vexans*. However, despite the wide range of potential mosquito vectors for RVFV, the virus has yet to be detected in other regions outside Africa and the Middle East, and the reasons for this are unknown. Although primarily a mosquito-borne viral disease [14,25,146,150,151], RVFV has also been isolated from an array of other haematophagous arthropods including ticks and sand flies, but their significance to transmission cycles has yet to be established [15,152–156]. However, this does raise the possibility that following introduction into Europe, RVFV could spread within populations of alternative haematophagous arthropods.

Without the availability of efficacious veterinary vaccines, the emergence of RVFV in Europe could have a potentially devastating impact on the agriculture industry, from both an animal health and an economic aspect. The cross-border livestock trade throughout Eastern Africa is one of the most significant areas of economic growth, and is estimated to exceed US\$60 million per year [157]. As a result of the 2007 outbreak in Tanzania, 52.4% of regions in the country were affected, resulting in an estimated loss due to livestock mortality of over \$4 million for cattle and \$2 million for sheep and goats, along with a significant decline in international animal trade [158]. Furthermore, outbreaks in domestic animal populations may also lead to transmission to humans through contact with infected livestock. The 2007 outbreak in Sudan resulted in 698 human cases, of which 222 were fatal (case fatality rate of 31.8%) [159]. Infection through direct contact with blood from infected animals has been reported in humans [160] and laboratory acquired infections have been documented [17,161]. With no human vaccine available, or effective antivirals, human death could result. This potential for infection by direct contact or aerosol, combined with severe clinical manifestations, has highlighted the possible utility of RVFV as a bio-weapon, and has generated renewed interest in animal models and vaccines [162].

5. Concluding remarks

A robust cohort of methods are readily available for the diagnosis of RVFV infection, therefore new cases are likely to be diagnosed efficiently in the event of an epidemic in Europe. However, the lack of an approved vaccine against RVFV for use in humans, along with limitations to veterinary vaccines, is a major concern. A change in climate to warmer and wetter conditions has the potential to increase the risk of incursion of additional competent mosquitoes for RVFV into Europe, and propagate existing mosquito populations. Additionally, in some *Aedes* species, infected diapaused eggs have been shown to survive during inter-epizootic, dry or cold periods, leading to the possibility of over-wintering [163]. If introduced into Europe, RVFV therefore has the potential to spread among local mosquito populations, with the potential to cause epidemics with significant impacts on human and animal health. Due to the threat of emergence outside Africa, veterinary vaccines

should be stockpiled in non-endemic areas [160]. The potential for future RVFV epidemics also drives an urgent requirement for an approved human vaccine. If the virus were to emerge outside the traditional endemic areas, the lack of an approved human vaccine, along with the potential for infection via direct contact or aerosol, the severity of clinical disease and the ease of access to samples, could threaten both humans and domestic animals. There is therefore an urgent requirement for a safe and efficacious human vaccine against RVFV infection, in addition to more reliable veterinary vaccines. Along with the need for improved vaccines, there are other considerations to help prevent an incursion of RVF into Europe. First, the spread of RVF throughout Africa needs to be limited, and this may be achieved through the stockpiling of vaccines, improved vaccination campaigns, and the provision of international funding to compensate affected farmers, who may otherwise be reluctant to report outbreaks within their herds. The OIE has created vaccine banks for a number of diseases, which is an important advance towards counteracting the global spread of animal diseases, and a RVFV vaccine bank is planned. In addition, a greater understanding of transmission pathways within Africa may help to prevent the spread of RVFV from Africa to Europe and other continents. This combined strategy would provide a truly One Health One World approach to what is considered one of the most serious arbovirus threats to human and animal health [164].

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